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COMBINED WORKPLAN WITH OBJECTIVES AND TEST DEFINITION FOR ALL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract:

This document describes the agreed plan of action for the Task 10.2, “Engineering of optimized cooling substrates”. The planned R&D activities aim at three objectives:

- Develop the process of cooling channel integration in CMOS into scalable solutions
- Define the optimal geometrical features attainable for 3D printed ultra-thin cold plates in metal alloys and ceramic composites
- Optimize the integration level of cooling features into ultra-light carbon composite structures

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2022

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

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Executive summary

Task 10.2 in AIDA innova targets the development of advanced and integrated solutions for the cooling of the next generation of Silicon vertex and tracking detectors. In this document, a detailed work plan is presented, with objectives and timelines for the development of a scalable process for the production of micro-channels integrated in the Silicon sensors, the development of 3D-printed cooling manifolds in several materials and the development of Carbon fibre composite support structures with integrated cooling circuits.

1. INTRODUCTION

The envisaged requirements for the next generation of vertex and tracking detectors, in terms of thermal performance, material budget and mechanical stability, will only be met through the deployment of innovative technologies, which are not yet available on the market. In the frame of WP10, T10.2 will focus on innovative solutions for integrated cooling devices and ultra-light structures. The ambition is to develop, in close collaboration with industrial partners, innovative solutions for the thermal management and the mechanical support of ultra-light silicon detectors. This will provide the detector designers with new possibilities not available today and will propel the innovation role of the European industry in the Hi-Tech sector by transferring to other fields the new technologies developed for High Energy Physics applications.

The production specialist partners involved in this Task are at the edge of the technology development in their specific fields. They will be all directly confronted with issues never tackled before, but well known to the research partners. Working hand in hand the team will identify optimal uses of new technologies emerging on the market to provide solutions to the issues. This will require pushing to the limits the technologies identifying intrinsic and improvable limitations. This knowledge will become part of the industrial partner background, positively impacting its position in the market for other applications. Furthermore, among the participating research partners several do have well developed capacities for small scale production in their field of expertise: the advanced knowledge developed during the project will then be available for technology transfer to other industrial partners both for larger scale productions targeting physics detectors and for future applications in other fields.

Three lines of action (sub-tasks) are foreseen within the task:

- A Develop the process of cooling channel integration in CMOS into scalable and mature solutions
- B Define the optimal geometrical features attainable for 3D printed ultra-thin cold plates in metal alloys and ceramic composites
- C Optimize the integration level of cooling features into ultra-light carbon composite structures

2. SCULPTING IN SILICON: INTEGRATED MICRO-CHANNELS IN SILICON SENSORS

2.1. GENERAL OBJECTIVES

Several high-energy-physics experiments have adopted micro-channel cooling in Silicon cooling plates as their cooling solution [1-2]. Integration of the cooling channels inside the sensor itself can improve the thermal contact further, while minimizing the material of the sensor.

The objective of this sub-task is to develop innovative and highly integrated solutions derived from modern micro-electronics techniques, like all-silicon support structures, to address the challenges posed by the combination of a minimal material budget and very stringent stability requirements for the future electron-positron colliders. Advanced MEMS-derived techniques enable the integration of the support structure, the signal and power lines and the cooling circuit in a single all-silicon ladder. The most important techniques are:

- -Selective etching and thinning of CMOS detectors to create a self-supporting ladder
- -Integration of micro-channels in silicon plates with integrated signal and power routing
- -Wafer-level post-processing to incorporate micro-channels in CMOS sensors

The activity builds on progresses made in AIDA2020, where the institutes involved managed to prove the principle of integrating support structures and cooling channels in standard detector-grade silicon sensors and in CMOS sensors [3-4].

The institutes involved will develop a CMOS-compatible process to integrate micro-channels at the wafer or at least "large-structure"-level. Two complementary lines will be followed, with CNM-IMB in Barcelona focussing on the exploration of eutectic wafer bonding, and MPG-HLL in Munich on direct bonding. Prototypes will be tested for bond quality at the production facilities, and further mechanical measurements and hydraulic characterization are foreseen at IFIC in Valencia.

Initially dummy structures with micro-channels in passive silicon will be targeted to assess the bond quality as a function of the process parameters (primarily temperature). Intermediate steps will see on the one hand the production of CMOS sensors with "all-silicon" support frames without micro-channels; and on the other hand – once a process theoretically compatible with CMOS is defined – the fabrication of proof-of-principle ladders with working CMOS circuits and a micro-channel cooling structure. In the final phase of the project, after completion of the preparation steps, the integration of actual CMOS sensors will be implemented.

2.2. SUB-TASK TIMELINE

The following table shows the planned timeline for the different activities:

Activity #		From	To
Activity A.1	CMOS-compatible bonding	March 2022	April 2023
	Optimization of bonding parameter for compatibility with CMOS devices Test samples: Unstructured and structured passive silicon wafers	14 months	

	Testing activities: Eutectic bonding and low-temperature direct bonding trials, bond quality tests, mechanical test, hydraulic characterizations		
Activity A.2.	All-silicon support frames and ladders	February 2023	December 2024
	Production of CMOS sensors with "all-silicon" support frames. Proof-of-principle ladders with working CMOS circuits and a micro-channel cooling structure Test samples: Testing activities: Mechanical and functional tests	23 months	
Activity A.3	Final demonstrators	April 2024	March 2025
	Integration of actual CMOS sensors in all-silicon ladders with integrated cooling channels Test samples: Fully functional detector ladder prototypes Testing activities: Mechanical, hydraulic circulation and functional tests.	12 months	

3. ULTRA-LIGHT 3D PRINTED COLD PLATES

The recent impressive progresses in Additive Manufacturing technologies (AM, or “3D-printing”) are making these innovative design and production processes more and more suited for different materials, and are rapidly decreasing the size of the minimum geometrical features attainable. Complex tri-dimensional heat exchangers, featuring geometries and performances otherwise unattainable with traditional technologies, are already in production for industrial applications.

The activity will leverage on two existing building blocks to make fully available the advantages of these techniques for the optimization of the next generation of semiconductor detectors:

- On the one hand the experience gained at CERN in the design of advanced silicon micro-channel cold plates of proven performances for silicon detector cooling
- On the other hand, the know-how acquired by CSEM and Lithoz in pushing to the highest accuracy 3D-printed geometrical features, and in tailoring different 3D-printable materials for different applications

By combining these building blocks, the activity aims at the generation of new standards to produce micro-structured cold plates produced by additive manufacturing, applicable to (ultra-thin wall) metallic alloys and ceramic materials. Because the ambition of WP10 is to prepare the road to cope with the challenging specifications for future application in very different kind of detectors (e.g. at hadron colliders or at lepton colliders), the focus is not on the production of prototypes of fully-defined cold plates but rather on the best attainable features respectively in terms of geometrical features, thermal-fluidic performances and mass minimization; and on the technological processes required to achieve them.

3.1. OBJECTIVES FOR METAL ALLOYS 3D PRINTING TECHNOLOGIES

3.1.1. AISi alloys

Considerable experience has been developed in the past by CSEM with the use of AISi12 (EN AC-44300) aluminium alloy, an interesting material for the targeted applications due to its low density, good mechanical properties and high thermal conductivity. Previous studies conducted by CSEM already demonstrated that the mechanical properties of components in metallic alloys produced by well-mastered AM processes are equal or superior to those coming from traditional production

techniques [5], therefore for this material the line of investigation will focus mainly on the attainable limits linked to the AM production process, and notably on:

- Minimum attainable ratio between inner diameter and pipe length for single pipes in:
 - Straight geometry
 - 180 degree-bent geometry
- Minimum attainable ratio between hydraulic diameter and channel length for multi-microchannel devices
- Minimum wall thickness attainable for leak-tight single pipes and multi-microchannel devices, including pressure resistance characterization
- Planarity attainable for flat multi-microchannel devices
- Characterization of dimensional manufacture accuracy with respect to target design features
- Inner wall roughness for single pipes and multi-microchannel devices

Samples of single pipes and multi-microchannel devices produced will also be submitted to long-test of fluid circulation in order to investigate the possible detachment of micro-particles from the inner walls of a fluidic device under different conditions and its evolution in time.

At the end of the activity demonstrators of a single pipe in 180-degree bent geometry and of a multi-microchannel device will be produced and thermally tested in existing test stands.

Both CSEM and CERN are equipped to conduct the dimensional measurements, while all fluidic tests including pressure, long-term circulation, and final thermal tests, will be conducted at CERN.

3.1.2. Low CTE alloys

While AlSi alloys present a very favourable stiffness to weight ratio (specific modulus) as compared to non-aluminium-based metal alloys, their CTE in the order of $20 \times 10^{-6} / \text{K}$ presents a severe mismatch with the CTE of silicon, typically spanning from 1.7 to $2.6 \times 10^{-6} / \text{K}$ in the temperature range $-50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $+25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This requires the insertion of a compliant thermal contact element between the metallic heat sink and the silicon heat source, leading to high inefficiencies. For this reason, low CTE alloys will also be studied: nickel-iron alloys, like Invar and Kovar, do match very closely the CTE of crystalline silicon. On the other hand, however, these materials feature values of thermal conductivity one order of magnitude lower than the one of AlSi alloys: a design- and specification-dependent balance between priorities to be given to thermal expansion or to thermal conductivity, together with considerations on the minimum wall thickness attainable, will in the end orient the choice of future detector designers.

Powders of both alloys, specifically conceived for AM applications are recently appearing on the market. In this case the activity will start from the analysis of the available powders, the evaluation of their printability, and the selection of the best candidate for the production of thermal management devices for detectors.

In a second phase, leveraging on the experience gained with the tests on AlSi alloys, the investigation activities defined in [section 3.1.1](#) will be repeated with the selected low CTE alloy, but only on a limited number of configurations.

Also for these activities it will be possible to conduct the dimensional measurements both at CSEM and at CERN, depending on the availability of resources and instrumentation, while all fluidic tests will be conducted at CERN. However, in this case final demonstrators of thermal management

devices will be produced and tested only if satisfactory level is provided by the selected technology during the dimensional and functional tests (pressure and fluid circulation). If the decision is taken to proceed with final demonstrators, the related thermal tests will also be conducted at CERN.

3.2. OBJECTIVES FOR CERAMIC 3D PRINTING TECHNOLOGIES

3.2.1. Alumina (Aluminium Oxide, Al_2O_3)

Following a similar strategy to the one adopted for metal-based AM, the investigation on the use of ceramic materials will move from the material best mastered by the industrial partner, Lithoz: Alumina (Al_2O_3). Alumina is by far the most common technical ceramic material used today, due to its broadly impressive material properties (including low density), ease of manufacture, wide availability, and budget-friendly cost. Also in this case, previous studies conducted by Lithoz already demonstrated that the mechanical properties of alumina components produced by well-mastered AM processes are comparable to those coming from traditional production techniques [6-7], therefore for this material the line of investigation will focus mainly on the attainable limits linked to the AM production process, and notably on:

- Minimum attainable ratio between inner diameter and pipe length for single pipes in:
 - Straight geometry
 - 180 degree-bent geometry
- Minimum attainable ratio between hydraulic diameter and channel length for multi-microchannel devices
- Minimum wall thickness attainable for leak-tight single pipes and multi-microchannel devices, including pressure resistance characterization
- Planarity attainable for flat multi-microchannel devices
- Control of dimensional manufacture accuracy with respect to target design features
- Inner wall roughness for single pipes and multi-microchannel devices

Samples of single pipes and multi-microchannel devices produced will also be submitted to long-test of fluid circulation in order to investigate the possible detachment of micro-particles from the inner walls of a fluidic device under different conditions and its evolution in time.

At the end of the activity demonstrators of a single pipe in 180-degree bent geometry and of a multi-microchannel device will be produced and thermally tested in existing test stands.

Both Lithoz and CERN are equipped to conduct the dimensional measurements, while all fluidic tests including pressure, long-term circulation, and final thermal tests, will be conducted at CERN.

However, less is known about radiation effects on ceramic materials than is on metallic alloys. Therefore, a selection samples from the same production batches, representative of the geometries produced, will be irradiated and submitted to a sequence of dimensional, mechanical (flexural strength following the norm ASTM C1161-13) and functional tests. Gamma irradiation up to doses of few MGy and Proton irradiation up to fluences of the order of 10×10^{16} $1\text{MeV}_{\text{neq}}/\text{cm}^2$ are presently envisaged. CERN will be in charge of the irradiation campaigns and of the post-irradiation test execution.

3.2.2. Aluminium Nitride (AlN)

Alumina exhibits a CTE of the order of 5 to 6×10^{-6} /K, only a factor 2 larger than the one of crystalline silicon, but it has a very low thermal conductivity. Aluminium Nitride (AlN) represents a very

interesting alternative material, exhibiting very similar mechanical properties and density, but a CTE more closely matching the one of crystalline silicon and a high thermal conductivity, above 150 W/m·K. Preliminary works performed at Lithoz [8] have recently shown that it is possible to produce AlN components by AM also in complex geometry, however the process parameters still need optimization and the postprocessing of the manufacture requires a high temperature annealing under inert atmosphere. For these reasons the activity will start from a critical review of the process and the definition of the optimal process to produce devices suited for detector thermal management.

Following the strategy adopted for the low CTE metal alloys, in a second phase, leveraging on the experience gained with the tests on Al₂O₃, the investigation activities defined in [section 3.2.1](#) will be repeated with the selected low CTE alloy, but only on a limited number of configurations.

Also for these activities it will be possible to conduct the dimensional measurements both at CSEM and at CERN, depending on the availability of resources and instrumentation, while all fluidic tests will be conducted at CERN. However, in this case the following phase of investigation of radiation effects, and production and test of final demonstrators of thermal management devices will be launched only if satisfactory levels are provided by the selected technology during the dimensional and functional tests (pressure and fluid circulation). If the decision is taken to proceed with final demonstrators, the related radiation tolerance and thermal tests will also be conducted at CERN.

3.2.3. Ceramic composites (“green parts”)

The consolidated approach to the production of ceramic components by AM starts from dense suspensions of ceramic powders into a photocurable polymeric binder. During the successive deposition steps of the suspension, the binder is selectively cured until the attainment of a manufacture in polymeric-ceramic composite reproducing the CAD designed-shape: the so-called “green part”. Through the following steps of thermal post-processing (de-binding and sintering), the final manufacture in ceramic of high purity is obtained. The thermal post-processing is always mandatory for most of the final applications using ceramic components, typically requiring very high purity and/or high stiffness and/or high electrical insulation. However, this induces a non-negligible shrinkage, potentially introducing some geometrical deformations due to anisotropy phenomena, and in some cases also some level of local porosity. Both these effects are highly undesirable for mini- and micro-fluidic applications, where the respect of very precise geometries at the microscale is important and the leak-tightness of the wall is of primary importance.

Lithoz and CERN will investigate the possibility of skipping the thermal postprocessing and directly produce cold plates as “green parts”. However, this requires a two-steps development: in first instance the polymeric binder presently adopted in the Lithoz process – optimized for sublimation during the thermal postprocessing – must be modified to provide good mechanical properties to the composite “green part”. However, the binder presently in use is an Acrylate, a class of polymers with poor tolerance to the ionizing radiations typical of Tracking and Vertex detectors: dedicated irradiation tests will be performed, but it is anticipated that sustainable ionising dose limits will be rather low. Therefore, in second instance, the development will orient towards the implementation of a process using a photo-curable rad-hard polymer as binder. Candidates will be in particular evaluated in the classes of epoxies and polyimides.

The sequence and the locations of the different tests will be the same than the one presented for the other ceramic materials, but the progress to the next phase of testing will be strongly conditioned by

the success in all the previous step, and the two partners might agree to stop the development if the results form the first steps are not satisfactory.

3.3. SUB-TASK TIMELINE

The following table shows the planned timeline for the different activities:

Activity #		From	To
Activity B.1.1	AlSi alloys AM technology limits	April 2022	March 2023
	Basic investigation on the geometrical limits attainable for hydraulic devices 3D-printed in AlSi alloy. Test samples: Standard mechanical samples and simple pipes Testing activities: Geometrical/dimensional analysis, hydraulic tests in pressure and circulation	12 months	
Activity B.1.2	AlSi alloys AM-produced demonstrators	April 2023	March 2025
	Functional exploration on demonstrators of hydraulic devices 3D-printed in AlSi alloy. Test samples: Simple pipes and multi-channel devices Testing activities: Hydraulic tests and thermal-fluidic characterization	23 months	
Activity B.1.3	Low CTE alloys AM technology limits	July 2022	December 2023
	Selection of the best suited low CTE alloy and basic investigation on the geometrical limits attainable for hydraulic devices 3D-printed with it. Test samples: Standard mechanical samples and simple pipes Testing activities: Geometrical/dimensional analysis, hydraulic tests in pressure and circulation	18 months	
Activity B.1.4	Low CTE alloy AM-produced demonstrators	January 2024	March 2025
	Functional exploration on demonstrators of hydraulic devices 3D-printed in the selected low CTE alloy. Test samples: Simple pipes and multi-channel devices Testing activities: Hydraulic tests and thermal-fluidic characterization	15 months	
Activity B.2.1	Aluminium oxide AM technology limits	April 2022	March 2023
	Basic investigation on the geometrical limits attainable for hydraulic devices 3D-printed in Aluminium oxide. Test samples: Standard mechanical samples and simple pipes Testing activities: Geometrical/dimensional analysis; hydraulic tests in pressure and circulation; mechanical tests; post-irradiation repetition of tests.	12 months	
Activity B.2.2	Aluminium oxide AM-produced demonstrators	April 2023	March 2025
	Functional exploration on demonstrators of hydraulic devices 3D-printed in Aluminium oxide. Test samples: Simple pipes and multi-channel devices Testing activities: Hydraulic tests and thermal-fluidic characterization	23 months	
Activity B.2.3	Aluminium nitride AM technology limits	July 2022	December 2023
	Selection of the best suited fabrication process and basic investigation on the geometrical limits attainable for hydraulic devices 3D-printed in Aluminium nitride.	18 months	

	<p>Test samples: Standard mechanical samples and simple pipes</p> <p>Testing activities: Geometrical/dimensional analysis; hydraulic tests in pressure and circulation; mechanical tests; post-irradiation repetition of tests.</p>		
Activity B.2.4	Aluminium nitride AM-produced demonstrators	January 2024	March 2025
	<p>Functional exploration on demonstrators of hydraulic devices 3D-printed in Aluminium nitride.</p> <p>Test samples: Simple pipes and multi-channel devices</p> <p>Testing activities: Hydraulic tests and thermal-fluidic characterization</p>	<p>15 months</p> <p>(Note: activity subject to positive results from B.2.3)</p>	
Activity B.2.5	“Green parts” technology limits	October 2022	March 2025
	<p>Selection of the best suited binder system and basic investigation on the geometrical limits attainable for hydraulic devices from 3D-printed “green parts”.</p> <p>Test samples: Standard mechanical samples and simple pipes</p> <p>Testing activities: Geometrical/dimensional analysis; hydraulic tests in pressure and circulation; mechanical tests; post-irradiation repetition of tests.</p>	<p>30 months</p>	

4. ULTRA-LIGHT COMPOSITE STRUCTURES WITH FULLY INTEGRATED COOLING

4.1. GENERAL OBJECTIVES

The general objective of this sub.task is the development of ultra-light carbon composite substrates for tracker sensors support and thermal management. A collaboration between CERN and Workshape (composite material) drives the research. The knowledge of the production will be transferred to Workshape that will support the Carbon Cold Plates and radiator sample production during 2022-2025.

This activity will focus on heat exchangers made of carbon fibre composites, named Carbon Cold Plates (CP), with embedded ultra-thin Polyimide pipes (micropipes). In parallel, the activity will investigate the possibility to produce heat exchangers made of carbon radiator for forced air cooling, to be used for very low power applications

In detail, the R&D will focus on the Carbon CP compatible with high-pressure liquid coolants like two-phase CO₂ refrigerant and new coolants, like Krypton. In a second step, the research will focus on the possibility to produce extended Carbon CP to cover large surfaces and understand their potentialities and limitations to embed microfluidic circuits considering minimum bending radius, pressure drop and pressure resistance limitations.

In parallel to the different studies on the Carbon CP, characterization of the polyimide pipes only, like pressure resistance, pressure drop, fluid compatibility and permeation tests, is foreseen to support and drive the Carbon CP design.

The design and production of heat exchangers made of carbon radiator for forced air cooling, used for very low power applications, will also be studied. The step of the research will investigate several design layouts and carbon materials with small-scale prototypes (10x10x6mm³). Mechanical characterization (air impedance, particles release, compression, CTE mismatch) and thermal characterization (heat transfer coefficient) for small-scale radiators samples will be done. Real-scale

radiators (approximately 600x600x6mm³) with the most promising design layouts will be then produced and characterized.

4.2. SUB-TASK TIMELINE

The following table shows the planned timeline for the different activities, for which it is intended that the testing phases will be performed at CERN on existing dedicated test stands:

Activity #		From	To
Activity C.0	Polyimide pipe characterization	April 2021	March 2024
	<p>Test samples: different pipe diameter, minimum bending radius, minimum thickness, polyimide braided.</p> <p>Testing activities: pressure resistance, pressure drop, fluid compatibility and permeation tests.</p>	36 months	
Activity C.1	Carbon CP and CO₂ compatibility	Sept. 2021	March 2023
	<p>CP design and manufacturing: optimization of cold plate design for CO₂, knowledge transfer of production process from CERN to Workshape.</p> <p>Test samples: Carbon CPs with embedded polyimide pipes of diameter range 0.3-2mm, Production of 4 lots (each lot 10 CPs)</p> <p>Testing activities: Pressure resistance, Thermal characterization</p>	18 months	
Activity C.2	Carbon CP compatibility with new coolant (Krypton,..)	April 2023	April 2024
	<p>CP design and manufacturing: optimization of cold plate design for new coolants.</p> <p>Test samples: Carbon CPs with embedded polyimide pipes of diameter range 0.3-2mm, Production of 4 lots (each lot 10 CPs)</p> <p>Testing activities: Pressure resistance, Thermal characterization</p>	12 months	
Activity C.3	Carbon CPs dimension limits	October 2024	March 2025
	<p>CP design and manufacturing: investigate minimum size CP (limit minimum pipe diameter) and largest size CP (limit pressure resistance). Production at Workshape company.</p> <p>Test samples: Carbon CPs with embedded polyimide pipes of diameter range 0.3-2mm, Production of 4 lots (each lot 10 CPs)</p> <p>Testing activities: Pressure resistance, Thermal characterization</p>	18 months	
Activity C.4	Gas cooling radiators comparison small scale	March 2022	September 2023
	<p>Radiator design and manufacturing: Design of optimised radiator for gas cooling in Carbon foam or alternative CFRP material, Investigation of possible interface Silicon sensor and radiator. knowledge transfer of production from CERN to Workshape.</p> <p>Test samples: small dimension radiators with different materials and designs 10x10x30mm³. Production of number of samples.</p> <p>Testing activities: mechanical characterization (air impedance, particles release, compression, CTE mismatch), thermal characterization (heat transfer coefficient).</p>	18 months	

Activity C.5	Gas cooling radiators real scale	Sept. 2023	September 2024
	<p>Radiator design and manufacturing: Design of real scale radiators for gas cooling of selected materials and designs.</p> <p>Test samples: real dimension radiators with different materials and designs 600x600x10mm³.</p> <p>Testing activities: mechanical characterization (air impedance, particles release, compression, CTE mismatch), thermal characterization (heat transfer coefficient).</p>	12 months	

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ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
CAD	Computer-Aided Design
CMOS	Complementary Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor
CP	Cold Plate
CTE	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion
MEMS	Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems